

Table 1: Interview questions and their relation with the RQs

Research questions (RQs) →	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Background questions								
1. What is the domain of your company and what kind of services does it provide?								
2. How long have you been working and what is your current role?								
Key questions								
3. What is your understanding of a DT?	×							
4. How are you involved in the development or usage of the DT?								
5. What problems are you solving with your DT?	×							
6. Is your DT for the entire process/system or a specific part?	×							
7. What are the main parts of your DT? Could you shortly describe their role?	×			×				
8. Is there a physical counterpart of your DT? Does it communicate with the digital world? If yes, how?	×		×					
9. Did you build your DT from scratch or you reused some of the things that already existed? What kind of issues did you face if you reused something or by building from scratch?		×					×	
10. How is the data exchange between the models (and physical system) specified?			×	×	×			
11. How is the sequence of execution of the models in your DT?					×			
12. What issues, if any, did you face with the overall collective execution of models in your DT?							×	
13. Which platforms/tools are you using to develop the digital twin?			×	×	×	×		
14. How often is the DT updated for bug fixes, improvement or similar reasons?			×					
15. After each update did you face integration issues? If yes, what kind?			×				×	
16. How do you ensure various software elements can work together specially if multiple tools were used for development?		×	×	×	×	×		
17. What properties/parameters did you validate to ensure an overall consistent behavior of your DT?							×	
18. What tools and techniques did you use to validate these properties and parameters?						×	×	
19. What do you consider to be the general characteristics of your DT?	×							
Concluding questions								
20. How do you see the DT evolve in the future to solve additional problems?								×
21. What is your opinion on the 5-dimensional DT model from Tao et al. [1]?	×							

References

- [1] TAO, F., ZHANG, M., LIU, Y., AND NEE, A. Digital twin driven prognostics and health management for complex equipment. *CIRP Annals* 67, 1 (2018), 169–172.